

Application of Diffusion Quantum Monte-Carlo Method for Neutron Diffusion Calculations

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ABSTRACT

The diffusion quantum Monte-Carlo method, which is used in other engineering/scientific fields such as thermal conduction and molecular dynamics, is applied to neutron diffusion calculation to provide a solution independent from the conventional deterministic diffusion method based on unstructured meshes. Comparisons with the analytic solution in homogeneous geometry and the numerical solutions in heterogeneous geometry show the validity of the present method.

Keywords: diffusion quantum Monte-Carlo, diffusion calculation, generalized geometry

1. INTRODUCTION

In the reactor physics field, the Monte-Carlo method is a reference method for neutron transport calculations. However, the Monte-Carlo method has also been a choice to solve a diffusion-type problem, such as the heat conduction [1][2] and the Schrödinger equations [3]. When the neutron diffusion equation can be solved by the Monte-Carlo method, a generalized geometry including a curvilinear surface can be handled without approximation. Therefore, the Monte-Carlo method can provide an alternative reference solution to a deterministic diffusion solution, e.g., obtained by the finite element method.

The diffusion quantum Monte-Carlo (DMC) method has been developed to numerically solve diffusion-type problems [1]-[3]. DMC utilizes the relation between the random walk process and the diffusion process, which is briefly described in Section 2.

The following sections are organized as follows: Section 2 provides the theoretical basis of the DMC. Numerical results are described in Section 3 for several simple problems, including homogeneous and heterogeneous geometries. Finally, the concluding remarks and the issues to be addressed are summarized in Section 4.

2. THEORY

2.1. Basics of the Diffusion Quantum Monte-Carlo Method

Let us consider a particle distribution probability in one dimension $p(x, t)$, normalized as:

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$$\int_{-\infty}^{\infty} p(x, t) dx = 1. \quad (1)$$

In the random walk, the temporal development of $p(x, t)$ can be written as [3]:

$$p(x, t + \Delta t) = \frac{1}{2}p(x + \Delta x, t) + \frac{1}{2}p(x - \Delta x, t), \quad (2)$$

where Δt and Δx are the time step size and moving distance of a random walk, respectively. By applying the Taylor series expansion for both sides of Eq. (2), we have:

$$\begin{aligned} p(x, t) + \frac{\partial}{\partial t}p(x, t)\Delta t &= \frac{1}{2}p(x + \Delta x, t) + \frac{1}{2}p(x - \Delta x, t) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \left(p(x, t) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x}p(x, t)\Delta x + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2}p(x, t)\Delta x^2 \right) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2} \left(p(x, t) - \frac{\partial}{\partial x}p(x, t)\Delta x + \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2}p(x, t)\Delta x^2 \right). \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Thus, it is reformulated as:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}p(x, t) = \frac{\Delta x^2}{2\Delta t} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2}p(x, t). \quad (4)$$

Equation (4) corresponds to a time-dependent diffusion equation as follows:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}p(x, t) = D \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2}p(x, t), \quad (5)$$

where the diffusion coefficient is defined by:

$$D = \frac{\Delta x^2}{2\Delta t}. \quad (6)$$

The above discussion indicates that the random walk process is equivalent to the diffusion process characterized by D .

2.2. Application of DMC to Neutron Diffusion Calculations

2.2.1. Calculation procedures

Based on the reference [3], the outline of calculation procedures in one-dimensional geometry is summarized as follows. It is noted that position and time are treated as dimensionless variables.

- (1) Generate a neutron from a neutron source. When the neutron source has a spatial distribution, randomly sample the position of a generated neutron based on the spatial probability distribution of the neutron source intensity.
- (2) Calculate $\langle \Delta \xi^2 \rangle = 2\Delta \tau$, $\Delta \tau = v\Delta t/D$, where ξ , τ , v , and D are dimensionless distance, dimensionless time, neutron speed, and the diffusion coefficient, respectively.
- (3) Randomly sample ξ from the normal distribution whose average and standard deviations are 0 and $\sqrt{2\Delta \tau}$, respectively. Convert $\Delta \xi$ to actual distance by $\Delta x = D\Delta \xi$.

- (4) Move a neutron using the distance Δx sampled in Step (3).
- (5) Tally region-integrated neutron scalar flux ϕ_i of region i by adding $D\Delta\tau$, which corresponds to the "track length" of the neutron.
- (6) Calculate neutron absorption probability by $1 - e^{-\Sigma_a D\Delta\tau}$
- (7) When the neutron is absorbed, go to Step (1).
- (8) When the neutron survives, go to Step (3).
- (9) Repeat Steps from (1) to (8) for N neutrons, where N is the neutron history.
- (10) The scalar flux for region i is calculated by $\phi_i/(\Delta x_i \times B)$, where Δx_i and B are the width of region i and $B = N/S$ where S is the spatially integrated neutron source intensity.

2.2.2. Extension to two- or three-dimensional geometry

In the case of two- or three-dimensional geometry, the DMC algorithm described in section 2.2.1 is extended as follows:

[Two-dimensional case]

- (3') Randomly sample moving distances from the normal distribution whose average and standard deviations are 0 and $\sqrt{2\Delta\tau}$ for x- and y-directions. Samplings are independently carried out for x- and y-directions.
- (4') Move the neutron in x- and y- directions using the sampled distances in Step (3').

[Three-dimensional case]

- (3'') Randomly sample moving distances from the normal distribution whose average and standard deviations are 0 and $\sqrt{2\Delta\tau}$ for x-, y-, and z-directions. Samplings are independently carried out for x-, y-, and z-directions.
- (4'') Move the neutron in x-, y-, and z-directions using the sampled distances in Step (3'').

One may wonder that the average moving distances are different among one, two, and three-dimensional cases. Actually, the square of the average distance between neutron birth and absorption places in one, two, and three-dimensional geometries are $2L^2$, $4L^2$, and $6L^2$, respectively, where L is the neutron diffusion length defined by $L = \sqrt{D/\Sigma_a}$. The difference corresponds to the neutron random walk in each Cartesian coordinate in one, two, and three-dimensional geometry.

2.2.3. External boundary conditions

In the following description, one-dimensional geometry is assumed. Extension to multi-dimensional geometry is straightforward.

[Reflective boundary condition]

The reflective boundary condition is treated as follows:

$$\begin{cases} x \rightarrow 2X^+ - x, & x > X^+ \\ x \rightarrow 2X^- - x, & x < X^- \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

where X^+ and X^- are the coordinates of the reflective boundary at x-plus and x-minus surfaces, respectively.

[Periodic boundary condition]

The periodic boundary condition is treated as follows:

$$\begin{cases} x \rightarrow X^- + x - X^+, & x > X^+ \\ x \rightarrow X^+ + x - X^-, & x < X^- \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

[Vacuum boundary condition]

A particle moving outside of the vacuum boundary is eliminated. However, it is noted that this treatment is not appropriate, as shown in the numerical calculation; thus, further consideration will be necessary.

[Zero-flux boundary condition]

The anti-reflective boundary condition is applied. Namely, the coordinate is handled by Eq. (7), but the weight of the particle has a negative value of the original weight. However, it is noted that this treatment may cause divergence of the weight of the neutron [4], thus further consideration will be necessary.

[Albedo boundary condition]

The reflective boundary condition is applied, and the weight of the particle is multiplied by the albedo value. This boundary condition is not tested in the present paper, but further consideration would be necessary.

2.2.4. Internal boundary conditions

The moving distance and absorption probability are modified for a particle crossing an internal boundary. Since the time step size should be sufficiently small to simulate the diffusion process, a particle is assumed to cross an internal boundary once during a move. Considering a neutron moving from region i to $i + 1$. The moving distance in region i is unchanged, while that in region $i + 1$ is adjusted as follows:

$$\Delta x_{i+1} = (\Delta x - \Delta x_i) \frac{D_{i+1}}{D_i} \quad (9)$$

where Δx , Δx_i and Δx_{i+1} are randomly sampled moving distance (sampled in region i), moving distance in region i , and that in region $i + 1$, respectively. Δx_i is calculated by the distance between the original position and the internal boundary. Neutron absorption probabilities are independently calculated in regions i and $i + 1$ using $1 - e^{-\Sigma_{a,i} D_i \Delta \tau_i}$ and $1 - e^{-\Sigma_{a,i+1} D_{i+1} \Delta \tau_{i+1}}$, respectively. Tally of neutron flux is also independently carried out in regions i and $i + 1$.

2.2.5. Choice of DMC parameters

In the fixed source neutron diffusion calculation using DMC, the number of neutron histories and time step size should be specified. The number of neutron histories and time step size have a direct impact on calculation accuracy and computation time.

The number of neutron histories is chosen from the viewpoint of the statistical error of the tally quantity. However, the time step size should be carefully chosen to reproduce the diffusion process by DMC. Since the approximate absorption rate in one step is given by $\Sigma_a D \Delta\tau$, the expected number of collisions for a neutron is $1/(\Sigma_a D \Delta\tau)$. For example, when $\Sigma_a = 0.1$ [1/cm], $\Delta\tau = 0.01$, and $D = 1$ [cm], expected number of collisions for a neutron is 10^3 . When the number of neutron histories is 10^4 , approximately 10^7 samplings and movings are necessary. To reduce computation time, a larger $\Delta\tau$ is desirable. However, when $\Delta\tau$ is too large, simulation results would deteriorate since the neutron diffusion process is not well reproduced.

3. NUMERICAL RESULTS

3.1. Infinite Homogeneous Geometry

For the proof of principle of DMC, the one-group fixed source problems with infinite 1D, 2D, and 3D homogeneous geometries are analyzed. A plane, line, and point sources are considered for 1D, 2D, and 3D geometries, respectively. The analytic solutions are used as the reference. The cross sections are as follows: $D = 1.0$ [cm], $\Sigma_a = 0.1$ [1/cm]. The DMC parameters are: $\Delta\tau = 0.001$, number of neutron histories= 10^6 . Comparison of neutron scalar flux distribution from origin (source) to 40 cm shows excellent agreement between the DMC results and the references, though no comparison is shown in this paper due to the limitation of pages.

3.2. Slab Geometry with External or Internal Boundary Condition

As the next step, verification calculations are carried out in the 1D slab geometry with the external or the internal boundary condition. The thickness of the slab is 10 cm ($-5 \leq x \leq +5$ cm) and the plane source is placed at $x = 0$. Calculation conditions are: $D = 1.0$ [cm], $\Sigma_a = 0.1$ [1/cm], $S=10^4$ [1/s/cm²], $\Delta\tau = 0.001$, number of neutron histories= 10^6 . The intensity of plane neutron source S is given by the number of neutrons released per second per unit area of plane source. Calculation results for the reflective and vacuum boundary conditions are shown in Figures 1 and 2. No systematic difference is observed in Figure 1, while a significant difference exists in Figure 2. The DMC result is closer to the analytic solution with the zero-flux boundary condition. The present result indicates that the vacuum boundary condition discussed in section 2.2.3 is not appropriate. Further discussion will be necessary to address this inconsistency.

Next, the internal boundaries are considered. In this case, the 1D slab has two different regions, which consist of region 1 ($-2.5 \leq x \leq +2.5$ cm) and region 2 ($-5 \leq x \leq -2.5, 2.5 \leq x \leq 5$ cm). Calculation conditions are: $D = 1.0$ or 0.5 [cm], $\Sigma_a = 0.1$ or 0.2 [1/cm], $S=10^4$ [1/s], $\Delta\tau = 0.001$, and number of neutron histories= 10^6 . Calculation results are shown in Figures 3 and 4. No systematic difference is observed in Figures 3 and 4. These results indicate that the treatment of the internal boundary condition is appropriate.

Though systematic analysis of statistical uncertainty is not investigated in the present study, the fluctuation in the calculation results suggest that the statistical uncertainty would be the order of 0.3% in the present calculation condition.

Figure 1. Comparison of neutron flux distribution (reflective boundary condition).

Figure 2. Comparison of neutron flux distribution (vacuum boundary condition).

Figure 3. Comparison of neutron flux distribution ($D_{reg1} = 1.0$, $D_{reg2} = 1.0$, $\Sigma_{a,reg1} = 0.1$, $\Sigma_{a,reg2} = 0.2$)

 Figure 4. Comparison of neutron flux distribution ($D_{reg1} = 1.0$, $D_{reg2} = 0.5$, $\Sigma_{a,reg1} = 0.1$, $\Sigma_{a,reg2} = 0.1$)

3.3. C5G7 Pin-cell Geometry

Finally, to investigate the applicability of DMC to general heterogeneous geometry and multi-group, a fixed source calculation is carried out in a 2D heterogeneous pin-cell geometry. The geometry and several group cross sections are taken from the C5G7 benchmark problem [5]. The spatially uniform fixed source ($1.0 [1/\text{cm}^3/\text{s}]$) is set to the pellet region only for the energy group 1. The cross section of the pellet region is UO_2 and that of the moderator region is moderator in the benchmark specification. Parameters of DMC are as follows: $\Delta\tau = 10^{-4}$, number of neutron histories = 5×10^5 . The reference result is obtained by an in-house diffusion code that can handle unstructured meshes based on the finite-volume method (FVM) with the cross-diffusion treatment [6]. A very fine mesh ($\sim 8,000$ meshes) is used to accurately model the pin-cell geometry, which includes curved surfaces. The strict comparison between the transport and diffusion calculations is not appropriate for the verification of DMC, the transport calculation is also carried out using the GENESIS code [7] based on MOC to provide additional information regarding to the transport effect in this problem.

Comparison of region average scalar fluxes is shown in Table I. DMC well reproduces the results obtained by FVM. Discrepancy is observed between the results of DMC and GENESIS due to the difference in the calculation method (diffusion and transport). As expected, the present result indicates that the MOC solution cannot be a substitute for the reference solution of the diffusion calculation.

Table I. Comparison of scalar flux in C5G7 pincell problem: unit [1/cm²/s].

Group	DMC		FVM		GENESIS		DMC/FVM		DMC/GENESIS	
	Pellet	Moderator	Pellet	Moderator	Pellet	Moderator	Pellet	Moderator	Pellet	Moderator
1	7.436	7.423	7.447	7.427	7.624	7.315	0.9985	0.9995	0.9753	1.0148
2	9.245	9.228	9.244	9.226	9.347	9.200	1.0001	1.0002	0.9891	1.0031
3	4.299	4.309	4.285	4.296	4.231	4.292	1.0031	1.0030	1.0159	1.0040
4	1.550	1.566	1.549	1.564	1.497	1.576	1.0011	1.0015	1.0359	0.9935
5	1.168	1.168	1.164	1.168	1.157	1.177	1.0027	1.0007	1.0094	0.9929
6	1.272	1.287	1.273	1.292	1.263	1.341	0.9994	0.9965	1.0074	0.9602
7	1.409	1.499	1.410	1.506	1.415	1.655	0.9994	0.9952	0.9960	0.9059

4. CONCLUSIONS

The diffusion quantum Monte-Carlo (DMC) method is applied to neutron diffusion calculations. Since DMC relies on the Monte-Carlo method, treatment of complicated geometry, including curved surfaces, is possible. The basics of DMC and discussions on the interface condition are provided.

The DMC is applied to infinite homogeneous geometry, 1D slab geometry, and 2D heterogeneous pin-cell geometry with the multi-group cross section with fixed source condition. In the infinite homogeneous geometry, DMC well reproduces the reference results in 1D (slab), 2D (cylinder), and 3D (sphere) geometries. In 1D slab geometry with the external boundary condition, significant deviations from the reference results are observed for the vacuum boundary condition. More appropriate treatment will be necessary for the vacuum boundary condition. In the heterogeneous pin-cell geometry, the DMC well reproduces the reference results obtained from the diffusion calculation obtained by unstructured meshes and the finite volume method.

The present study reveals the advantages and issues of the DMC applied to neutron diffusion calculations. Since the DMC has geometric flexibility, it has the capability to provide a reference solution to diffusion calculation for complicated geometries, which is considered an independent solution from that of the conventional deterministic method.

As a future study, further discussion on the external conditions (vacuum, zero, and albedo boundary conditions) is necessary.

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